

A BRIEF REVIEW OF THE STUDY OF PHRASEOLOGISMS IN TURKIC STUDIES AND KARAKALPAK LINGUISTICS

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Annotation: The scientific article focuses on the study of phraseologisms in Turkic linguistics and works on phraseologisms in Karakalpak linguistics.

Keywords: phraseology, style, fixed expression, vocabulary.

Works on phraseologisms in Turkic linguistics began to be published after the 40s of the 20th century. The topics of research works on phraseologisms are diverse. After the 50s, phraseologisms began to develop as a separate discipline in Turkic linguistics. The first scientific opinion about stable combinations in Turkic languages in general dates back to S.N. Muratov's work "Stable combinations in the Turkic language" (M., 1961)[7.131].

If we review the published studies on the issue of phraseologisms, it is noticeable that there are a number of fruitful works in Turkic linguistics. Each nation belonging to the Turkic peoples has studied the stable phrases in its language, revealed their meanings, and divided them into different groups. The published studies of linguistic scientists on phraseologisms are evidence of this.

One of the first scientists to study Turkic phraseology was the Kazakh scientist I. Kenesbayev. It is considered that after the beginning of Kazakh phraseology, the Uzbek scholar of linguistics Sh. Rakhmatullayev[9], Azerbaijan – G.A. Bayramov [2], Turkmen – L. Babayev [1], Karachay-Balkar – Z.K. Zharashueva [6], Kyrgyz – Zh.Osmonova [8], Turkish - L.N. Dolganov [5], Kumyk – K.Kh. Daibova [4], Chuvash - M.F. Chernov [12], Phraseologisms in the Karakalpak language – E.Berdimuratov [3] and others. The works of the languages are considered the first principles of phraseology in Turkic linguistics. Of course, these works were the starting point for phraseological research. Although phraseologisms have been considered in new scientific directions in recent years, they originate from these studies.

Guldarkhan Smagulova, a scholar who has extensively studied phraseologisms in Kazakh linguistics, said in her study of Turkic phraseology: "When discussing the issues of Turkic phraseology, one should talk about the past development and formation of phraseologisms in Turkic studies, current research directions, and future status of stable phrases - one of the branches of spiritual values of the common Turkic culture"[10.256].

In Turkic linguistics, there are many scholars who have studied phraseologisms in various thematic groups. Some of the scientific works are devoted to the system of stylistic use of phraseologisms in the literary language, while others have studied phraseologisms in the works of individual writers. The issues of translating and comparative study of phraseologisms from other languages have not been left out of the research.

For the first time, the general problems of phraseologisms were studied in the work of Professor E. Berdimuratov. Later, Zh. Eshbayev's work "A Brief Phraseological Dictionary of the Karakalpak Language" was published. This work is considered the first phraseological dictionary in the Karakalpak language. S.T. Nauryzbayeva's dictionary is intended for a comparative study of phraseologisms in the Russian language and phraseologisms in the Karakalpak language. G. Ainazarova discussed the stylistic use of equivalent two-component phraseologisms in the Karakalpak language and the features of their use in literary works. A. Pirniyazova's work studied phraseologisms of the Karakalpak language as a system. The stylistic possibilities of phraseologisms were comprehensively studied on the basis of the works of famous writers. B. Yusupova considered phraseologisms from several perspectives. Her monograph "Phonic Analysis of Phraseologisms in the Karakalpak Language" was published. The monograph discusses the main features of euphonic phraseologisms in the Karakalpak language, their place in the phraseological system of the Karakalpak language and their study.

Of course, these works are part of the works studied in the field of phraseology in Karakalpak linguistics. In addition, a number of works, dissertations, and scientific articles on phraseologisms have been published in Karakalpak linguistics. However, research on phraseologisms is still considered a research problem, unlike other Turkic peoples.

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